

Legal aspects of HET: Germany

[WP3 – Human enhancement]

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Executive summary

In this report we give an overview on HET specific national legislation and legal developments in Germany. There is an ongoing debate in medical ethics regarding HET in Germany. Although the legal scholarship debate is rather small. HET is not directly addressed in the national legislation. Nevertheless, it is possible to find in the German legislation some specific laws and regulations that address particular issues related to HET, especially in the German Anti-Doping-Code, in the Act on medical devices, in the Social Insurance Code V and in the guidelines for physicians. The rules for doping in sports are relatively clear. However the rules for the use of enhancing drugs and the rules for financing HET treatments by the public health system give room for interpretation. Furthermore, there are many legal uncertainties due to slippery slopes between medical versus non-medical treatment, or therapeutic versus non-therapeutic interventions.

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
HET	Human Enhancement Technologies

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

1. Introduction

The objective of this report is to analyse the German law relevant for HET developments. The primary method used in preparing this report is desk research.

2. Scope and limitations of the report

This report has a limited scope as demarcated by the SIENNA task 3.2 workplan and guidelines.

3. Part I: Summary of legal developments and an analysis of national legal scholarship

3.1 Legal developments

Doping in sports

In Germany there have been legal developments regarding the regulation for doping in sports. Since 2015 Germany has an Anti-Doping-Law. The Federal Ministry of Justice and Consumer Protection, the Federal Ministry of the Interior and the Federal Ministry of Health presented a first draft on November 12, 2014. Professional organisations, e.g. the national Anti Doping Agency (NADA) were included in the drafting process. On 17th December 2015, the law came into force.

All criminal doping offenses, which were previously recorded in the Medical Act, are now regulated in the Anti-Doping-Act. Self-doping is prohibited by prison time. For the first time specifically athletes that dope themselves, intending to gain the advantages of doping in organized sport, are included in the law. Also the acquisition and possession of small amounts of doping products for self-doping are punishable. In addition, the rules for backers were tightened. The new anti-doping law helps the law enforcement agencies to dismantle doping networks.¹

Debate on enhancing drugs in Germany (pharmacological neuro-enhancement)

In Germany there is currently a debate on the use of prescription drugs for neuro-enhancement purposes, such as methylphenidate and modafinil. This topic is more in focus since 2009. In this year the German health insurance company „DAK“ published its annual Health Report with special focus on “doping at the workplace” and conducted both a survey of experts and an online survey of 3.000 people insured by the DAK.² The experts suspected “that drug use seems to be a socially accepted form of behaviour in everyday life and at work for coping with pain, discomfort, work pressure, stress, etc.”³ The evaluation of the online survey, however, showed that about 5 % of people in regular employment between the ages of 20 and 50 took brain-doping agents without medical necessity. Another study, published by the DAK in 2015 showed that around 3 Million Germans used prescriptions drugs to enhance their performance in working life.⁴

¹ Anti-Doping Act of 10 December 2015.

² DAK, Deutsche Angestellten-Krankenkasse (eds.), DAK Gesundheitsreport, Hamburg, 2009.

https://www.iges.com/e6/e1621/e10211/e6061/e6064/e6199/e9682/e9684/attr_objs9687/DAK_Gesundheitsreport_2009_ger.pdf

³ *ibid*, p. 84.

⁴ Marschall, J., and H.-D. Nolting et al., “Gesundheits-Report 2015, Analyse der Arbeitsunfähigkeitsdaten, Update: Doping am Arbeitsplatz”, 2015. <https://www.dak.de/dak/bundes-themen/gesundheitsreport-2015-1585966.html>.

In August 2018 the German Bundestag published a document reflecting this debate.⁵ Following the German law it is currently prohibited to use prescribed drugs with an off-label use. Furthermore, the use of narcotics for neuro enhancement is prohibited. According to the German basic law Art. 2 (1) each individual has the “right to self-harm”. Therefore, the consumption of neuroenhancing drugs is itself usually not punishable. However, the possession or acquisition of the respective preparations may very well be prohibited, with substantial legal differences arising from the nature of the substances consumed. Many prescription drugs, as well as drugs from the black market, which are consumed for the purpose of Neuroenhancements contain substances that are subject to the provisions of the German Narcotics Act (BtMG). For example, if an adolescent has received a methylphenidate-containing drug for the treatment of his ADHD, but he passes it to a friend who wants to take it to increase his cognitive performance, both violate the BtMG.

Aesthetic enhancement through cosmetic surgeries

For plastic surgeries for cosmetic reasons the same regulations apply than for medical surgeries in general, namely the professional code of conduct for physicians (“Musterberufsordnung”⁶), the national medical regulation (“Bundesärzteordnung”⁷) and the Social Insurance Code (Sozialgesetzbuch V). Reinhard Damm discussed in an article on “aesthetic surgery and medical law in Germany” regulatory problems in this field.⁸ Furthermore the central ethics commission at the German Medical Council⁹ published a statement on medical treatments in non-therapeutic field and focused especially on aesthetic surgery.¹⁰ The ZEKO deals with question if the state should determine on a legal basis whether physicians are allowed to carry out non-therapeutic interventions. This. Might conflict with certain rights physicians have in Germany, namely the freedom to choose occupation (“Berufsfreiheit”, Art. 12 Abs. 1 German basic law), the right to free development of his/her personality (“allgemeine Handlungsfreiheit”, Art. 2 Abs. 1 German Basic law), and for physicians working in research the freedom of research (“Wissenschaftsfreiheit”, Art. 5 Abs. 3 German basic law). On the other hand the government needs to protect the health of the population and this could be affected by non-therapeutic interventions that might cause physical or psychological harm. §1 of the national medical regulation (“Bundesärzteordnung”) says that a physician serves for the health of individuals and the whole population and furthermore the medical profession is not a trade or industry. The medical profession must be a free occupation. The ZEKO rules out in its statement that diseases and their treatment are still the core field of the medical profession. However, the definition of “disease” or “illness” and “health” is slippery slope. There is no clear line between therapeutic and non-therapeutic treatments. Based on this, the ZEKO recommends that physicians should carry out non-therapeutic treatments. The most legitimate reason is, in view of the ZEKO, that treatments otherwise may be

⁵ Deutscher Bundestag, Informationen zu Neuroenhancement, 2018.

<https://www.bundestag.de/blob/572364/c62698c6de2b0c74477a44cc24a83c97/wd-9-060-18-pdf-data.pdf>

⁶ (Muster-)Berufsordnung für die in Deutschland tätigen Ärztinnen und Ärzte – MBO-Ä 1997 – in der Fassung der Beschlüsse des 121. Deutschen Ärztetages 2018 in Erfurt, 2018.

(Guidelines for physicians in Germany)

⁷ Bundesärzteordnung 2016. Bundesärzteordnung in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 16. April 1987 (BGBl. I S. 1218), die zuletzt durch Artikel 5 des Gesetzes vom 23. Dezember 2016 (BGBl. I S. 3191) geändert worden ist. (national guidelines for physicians)

⁸ Damm R., “Ärztliches Berufsrecht, Arzthaftungsrecht. Ästhetische Chirurgie und Medizinrecht – Normstrukturen, Regelungsprobleme und Steuerungsebenen”, Gesundheitsrecht (GesR), 12, 2010. http://www.gesr.de/media/Aufsatz_GesR_12_2010.pdf

⁹ ZEKO, Website: <http://www.zentrale-ethikkommission.de/>

¹⁰ ZEKO 2012, Zentrale Ethikkommission bei der Bundesärztekammer, “Ärztliche Behandlungen ohne Krankheitsbezug unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der ästhetischen Chirurgie”, 2012. http://zek.schaffrath-digital.de/downloads/Stellungnahme_aesthetische_Chirurgie.pdf

carried out by less competent persons, which may cause a lot of physical harm. Although the ZEKO points out that for therapeutic and non-therapeutic medical interventions the same quality standards apply, e.g. informed consent, no-harm, no risk.¹¹

The leading opinion in Germany is that in the case of non-therapeutic procedures requirements concerning informed consent and risk assessment are more rigorous than in the case of procedures with a therapeutic aim.

There have been no further attempts or plans to adopt at national level new legislation or set up new regulatory bodies in response to developments or increased use of human enhancement technologies, nor attempts to regulate how HETs are designed, set up, commissioned or used.

3.2 Legal scholarship

3.2.1 Method used

In order to identify the relevant national legal literature three databases were used:

- Google scholar
- Juris (www.juris.de)
- BELIT (<http://www.drze.de/belit/>)

The following search terms were used (in German language and in English language) for a desktop search:

Search term	
ENGLISH	GERMAN TRANSLATION
Human enhancement	Verbesserung des Menschen , Leistungssteigerung
Non-therapeutic human enhancement	Nicht-therapeutische Eingriffe/Verbesserung/Steigerung
Non-therapeutic services	Nicht-therapeutische Verbesserungen des Körpers/der Kognition
Non-therapeutic medical services	Nicht-therapeutische medizinische Interventionen/Eingriffe Eingriffe
Aesthetic medicine	Schönheitschirurgie, Schönheitsoperationen
doping	doping
Enhancing drugs	Leistungssteigernde Medikamente
Wishful medicine	Wunschmedizin/Wunsch erfüllende Medizin

3.2.2 Overview of the selection of relevant literature

The term „enhancement“ is very popular in the German academic debate on medical ethics and rather unknown in the legal scholarship. There are no laws or guidelines using the term “enhancement”. And also in the case law this term is not used. The most common German legal data base “Juris” brings a few matches, e.g.:

- Gärditz, F., “Pharmakologisches Neuro-Enhancement als Rechtsproblem“, PharmR, 2011, pp. 46 ff.

¹¹ ZEKO 2012, Zentrale Ethikkommission bei der Bundesärztekammer, “Ärztliche Behandlungen ohne Krankheitsbezug unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der ästhetischen Chirurgie”, 2012. http://zek.schaffrath-digital.de/downloads/Stellungnahme_aesthetische_Chirurgie.pdf, pp. A2001-2003.

- Kunz, E., “Gehirndoping, Unheil oder Segen”, *MedR*, 2010, pp. 471 ff.
- Lindner, J.F., “Neuro-Enhancement als Grundrechtsproblem”, *MedR*, 2010, pp. 463 ff.

To find more relevant academic literature other search terms than “enhancement” are necessary (see table above). The search with these terms showed that mainly three questions are discussed in the legal scholarship debate on HET

1. Are neuroenhancement techniques and/or the use of enhancing drugs permitted or prohibited by the German law. Do we need new regulations in this field?¹²
2. Is the use of enhancing techniques for non-therapeutic purposes compatible with responsible medical conduct? What are potential consequences for the physician-patient-relationship?¹³
3. Which enhancing interventions should be paid by the public health system and which not?
 - a. SGB V, § 52 (2): If the insured persons have a disease through a not medicinally indicated cosmetic surgery, a tattoo or a piercing, the health insurance company can claim from the insurance person that he or she covers the costs at least partially.
 - b. <https://www.g-ba.de/institution/themenschwerpunkte/arszneimittel/lifestyle/> § 34 Abs. 1 Satz 7 SGB V: Exclusion of lifestyle-drugs from public health system financing

4. Part II: Analysis of specific legal issues

4.1 Terminology and legal demarcations

Question 1: Does the domestic law in your country provide a legal definition of “health” or the state of “health”? If yes, please quote the relevant source. Has the question of the definition of “health” been addressed in the case law?

No. According to the Basic Law for the Federal Republic of Germany Art. 2 (2): “Every person shall have the right to life and physical integrity.” Beside this right to life and physical integrity, the domestic law in Germany provides no legal definition of “health”. Pestalozza described this in an article: “A fundamental ‘right to health’ is expressly guaranteed by the constitutions of several Bundesländer, but unknown to the German Federal Constitution. Instead the Federal Constitutional Court has – especially on the basis of related human rights – developed the obligation of the State to protect everybody’s life and physical integrity, which in some respects comes near to a ‘right to health’”.¹⁴

There is an ongoing debate regarding the question if humans should or rather can have a right to health. The definition of health published by the WHO is often used in Germany. Although the leading opinion in the German legal scholarship debate is that it is not necessary, or rather not helpful to include this definition in the German law. The main critic is that this definition is based on subjective criteria.¹⁵

¹² This question is discussed e.g. in: Lindner, J.F., “Neuro-Enhancement als Grundrechtsproblem”, *MedR*, 2010, pp. 463 ff.; Gärditz, F., “Pharmakologisches Neuro-Enhancement als Rechtsproblem”, *PharmR*, 2011, pp. 46 ff.

¹³ See e.g. Schöne-Seifert, B., „Von der Medizin zur Humantechnologie? Ärztliches Handeln zwischen medizinischer Indikation und Patientenwunsch“ (From Medicine to Human Technology? Medical Treatment between Therapeutic Indication and the Wishes of the Patient), *Biopolitik*, 2005, pp. 179-199 and Viehhöver, W. and P. Wehling, *Entgrenzung der Medizin. Von der Heilkunst zur Verbesserung des Menschen* (Removing of Boundaries in Medicine. From Healing Arts to the Improvement of Humans), transcript, Bielefeld, 2011.

¹⁴ Pestalozza C., “Das Recht auf Gesundheit Verfassungsrechtliche Dimensionen”, *Bundesgesundheitsblatt*, 2007.

¹⁵ For this debate see e.g. Laufs, A., *Handbuch des Arztrechts*, Beck, 2010 and Bundesärztekammer, *Gesundheits- und sozialpolitische Vorstellungen der deutschen Ärzteschaft*, 1986.

Question 2: What are the basic legal terms and demarcations used nationally that should be taken into consideration in the discussion on the regulation of HET? and Question 3: What criteria are used to classify services, devices and products according to those categories?

The basic legal categories relevant for the discussion of the (future) regulation of HET in Germany include:

- A medical act (*medizinischer Eingriff*)
- A medical device¹⁶ (*medizinisches Instrument*)
- A medical product¹⁷ (*Medizinprodukt*)
- A therapeutic versus non-therapeutic medical act (*therapeutischer versus nicht-therapeutischer medizinischer Eingriff*)¹⁸
- A hazardous product (*Gefährliches Produkt*)

Enhancement services (procedures)

In the case of services, the most relevant term to consider in the discussion on the regulation of HET seems to be the notion of a “medical activity” (or a “medical act”, *medizinischer Eingriff*). There is no German law or guideline, which defines these terms.

Enhancement devices and products

In the case of “enhancement devices”, the relevant national legislation is a result of the implementation of the EU law.

1. Enhancement devices that are classified as medical devices

The first category of devices that could be used for enhancement purposes are devices that are at the same time classified as medical devices. The German Act on medical devices¹⁹ provides a definition of a medical device, which corresponds with the definition in the Council Directive 93/42/EEC of 14 June 1993 concerning medical devices. According to Section 3 of the German medical devices Act,

“Medical devices are all instruments, apparatus, appliances, software, substances or preparations made from substances or other articles, used alone or in combination, including the software intended by the manufacturer to be used specifically for diagnostic or therapeutic purposes and necessary for the medical device's proper application, intended by the manufacturer to be used for human beings, by virtue of their functions, for the purpose of

- a) diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, treatment or alleviation of disease,
- b) diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation or compensation of injuries or handicaps,
- c) investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological process or,
- d) control of conception, and which do not achieve their principal intended action in or on the human body by pharmacological,

¹⁶ See Act on the medical devices implementing the Council Directive 93/42/EEC of 14 June 1993 concerning medical devices.

¹⁷ See Directive 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 November 2001 on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use.

¹⁸ Used in the case law and the legal doctrine.

¹⁹ German Act on Medical Devices.

immunological or metabolic means, but which might be assisted in their function by such means.”

2. Enhancement devices that are not “medical devices”

Devices that can be used for enhancement, but whose purpose according to the manufacturer is not “medical”, are held to basic standards of product safety. In the case of all devices, the general rules on product liability apply. These are laid down in the German Product Liability Act²⁰.

4.2 Right to integrity of the person, legal permissibility of non-therapeutic services on the human body

Question 1: Does the domestic law recognize the right to (physical and/or mental) integrity of the person? If yes, please provide a relevant citation. What are the limits to this right? Please provide examples. What criteria and values are considered to set those limits?

According to Art. 2 (2) of the German basic law on personal freedoms, “(2) Every person shall have the right to life and physical integrity. Freedom of the person shall be inviolable. These rights may be interfered with only pursuant to a law.” A classic example of the state interfering with this right is the killing of a criminal that threatens the life of a hostage.

Questions 2: How is the legality of enhancement procedures (understood as non-therapeutic interventions in the human body) established?

As already mentioned above, “enhancement” per se is not regulated in the German law. Although some actions that might be considered as enhancing technologies are regulated, especially cosmetic surgery, doping in sports, gene editing and the use of enhancing drugs.

- Cosmetic surgery: Here the same rules apply that regulate the performance of medical surgeries – the regulations for medical professionals and the SGB.
- Doping in sports: The German Anti-Doping-Law regulates this field since 2015.
- Gene editing: Enhancing gene editing techniques or rather genetic human enhancement in general is prohibited by the German Embryo Protection Act and the Genetic Engineering Act.
- Enhancing drugs: The use of enhancing drugs is regulated in the Germans Pharmaceuticals Act (Arzneimittelgesetz, AMG) and the Narcotics Act (Betäubungsmittelgesetz, BtMG)

Question 3: Are there limits to what non-therapeutic procedures can be performed on a human body? What criteria are used to establish those limits? What is the role of consent? Does the national law, case-law or legal doctrine provide any guidance on how risks and benefits of non-therapeutic procedures should be weighed and/or what is the acceptable level of risk in those cases?

On the one hand plastic surgeries are non-therapeutic, although they can be performed only by physicians. On the other hand there are some non-therapeutic procedures which could be performed by everyone, e.g. tattooing and piercing.²¹ There is currently a debate in Germany regarding the question if laser techniques to erase tattoos should be performed only by physicians. The Federal Ministry for the Environment has drafted a regulation for the modernization of the radiation protection law.²² So far, tattoos removal by lasers could be carried out by anyone without the need for any special

²⁰ Product Liability Act of 15 December 1989.

²¹ If tattooing and piercing count as cosmetic enhancement, may of course be questionable.

²² Bundesministeriums für Umwelt, Naturschutz und nukleare Sicherheit 2018.

qualifications, even though such applications involve significant health risks to the person being treated. This regulatory gap should be closed with the new regulation.

Moving healthy body parts:

The question if the replacement of a healthy body part for a prosthetic one would be considered illegal cannot be answered clearly. The German Criminal Code is relevant. Section 228 says: „Whosoever causes bodily harm with the consent of the victim shall be deemed to act lawfully unless the act violates public policy, the consent notwithstanding.“ If this act violates public policy or not needs clarification from case to case.

Question 4: Has the question about the protection afforded to the augmented or modified body (e.g. body with prosthetics) been addressed nationally? Is the augmented or modified body (afforded the same protection and guarantees as an organic body? Are there issues about ownership?

Not identified.

5. Conclusion

The search for HET relevant law, legal developments and academic articles from legal scholars in Germany showed that there is not much out there at the moment. Although there is a discussion and some relevant legislation.

The most relevant German laws for HET are:

- The **Anti-doping Code**, which regulates since 2015 doping in sports.
- The Germans **Medicinal Products Act** (Arzneimittelgesetz – AMG) which regulates the use of enhancing drugs in connection with the **Narcotics Act** (Betäubungsmittelgesetz – BtMG.)
- The **German Act on Medical Devices**, which provides a definition of medical devices.
- The **Social Insurance Code V**, which entails information regarding the question which HET activities can/should be paid by the public health insurance companies.
- The **German basic Law** (Grundgesetz-GG) which contains
 - rights for persons who want to profit from HET, e.g. the “right to self-harm”, the “right to life and physical integrity”, and
 - rights for German physicians, e.g. the freedom to choose occupation (12(1)GG “Berufsfreiheit”) and the right to free development of his/her personality (2(1) GG “allgemeine Handlungsfreiheit”).
- **Guidelines for physicians** („Berufsordnung für Ärztinnen und Ärzte“).
- The **Embryo Protection Act** which prohibits gene editing.

The rules for doping in sports are relatively clear. However the rules for the use of enhancing drugs and the rules for financing HET treatments by the public health system need interpretation. Furthermore, there are many legal uncertainties, e.g. if the replacement of a healthy body part for a prosthetic one by a physician would be considered illegal and where to drop a line between therapeutic and non-therapeutic treatments, since there is no definition of “health” or “wellbeing” in the German law. Further questions are:

- Do we need new regulations for the use of enhancing drugs in Germany?
The use of enhancing drugs, especially at work, is, as mentioned above, a big issue in Germany.
- Is the use of enhancing techniques for non-therapeutic purposes compatible with responsible medical conduct?

The Central ethics commission at the German Medical association (ZEKO) points out that for non-therapeutic interventions/treatments the same rules have to apply than for therapeutic interventions, e.g. informed consent, no-harm, no-risk.

- What are potential consequences for the physician-patient-relationship?
- Which enhancing interventions should be paid by the public health system and which not?

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